

Value Sensitive Design based Approach for Trustworthiness including Ethics in Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract. The lack of trust in artificial intelligence (AI) slows its adoption across industries and society, usually due to limited understanding of how AI works and its advantages, and of how its trustworthiness including its ethical impact are assessed during development. Designing and validating a reliable AI system is complex, requiring inputs from various stakeholders throughout the development process. Ensuring that their concerns are systematically addressed remains a challenge. In this paper, a Value Sensitive Design (VSD) based approach to AI trustworthiness including ethics is presented. VSD integrates ethical values into technological design, and based on this approach a values reference model and an implementation method are defined for a trustworthy and ethical AI. In this paper, the experimentation of this approach in a use case involving collaborative robots is presented, addressing both technical and human-related characteristics of the AI systems. The preliminary findings in the work suggest that: (1) AI Trustworthiness is a broad concept that must be analysed in detail, considering industrial context and other priorities, (2) Achieving a shared understanding among stakeholders is essential but difficult, highlighting the need for structured dialogue, (3) Adopting this VSD based approach may have a significant impact on the stakeholders' minds.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Trustworthy AI, Ethical AI, Value Sensitive Design.

1 Introduction

“The integration of AI-based solutions into products and services has elicited growing concerns regarding their potential impact on fundamental rights and safety risks posed to users. Notably, apprehensions have been raised regarding the potential infringement on key rights such as non-discrimination, freedom of expression, human dignity, protection of personal data, and privacy” [1]. Ensuring societal trust in AI, Data and Robotics is part of the 2025-2027 mission of European industries. There are many misconceptions and much misinformation about AI, Data and Robotics in societal debates, and the technology is not fully accepted by society in all application areas. This will slow uptake, particularly where mistrust is unfounded, and may also damage markets where genuine risks are not properly addressed [2].

“Trustworthiness must be built up from the design phase of the systems, and this means building responsibly from the top down, bottom up, and throughout the AI lifecycle” [3]. However, current design practices often lack structured processes that make ethical and trustworthy principles traceable and actionable across the AI lifecycle. Trustworthiness by design for AI, concepting and designing human-centric AI systems that embed the technical foundations of trustworthy AI across industrial applications, is still a challenge. It is established as a medium-term objective as part of the Strategic Research, Innovation, and Deployment Agenda 2025-2027 published by the AI Data Robotics Association for Europe [4]. Designing and validating a trustworthy AI system is complex, requiring inputs from various stakeholders throughout the AI lifecycle, from conception to retirement. “Demonstrating the achievement of functional technology and how organizations are subject and responsive to regulation to mitigate risks are two key approaches to evaluate and demonstrate trustworthiness to different stakeholders” [5].

The purpose of this study is to define, implement and test a values reference model and an implementation method for trustworthiness including ethics end-to-end approach for AI solutions. The aim is to answer the following research questions (RQ): (RQ1) Is trustworthiness and ethics requirements implementation being assessed from technical and human viewpoints?; (RQ2) Is trustworthiness and ethics requirements implementation being assessed by different means?; (RQ3) Are the different stakeholders prioritising the same trustworthiness and ethics requirements?; (RQ4) What is the end-user feedback regarding trustworthiness including ethics?; (RQ5) How are the ethics and legal safeguards being implemented?

This paper is organised into the following sections: (1) Introduction, (2) Trustworthiness including ethics values reference model and implementation method – this section presents the elements of the approach defined, (3) Results – this section presents the findings of the approach implemented in a cobots industrial context and (4) Conclusions – this section presents general conclusions, identified limitations and future work.

2 Values reference model and implementation method for trustworthiness including ethics in AI

The development of a trustworthy and ethical AI requires both (1) a reference model and (2) an implementation method to integrate trustworthiness and ethical values during the AI lifecycle. In this section both works are presented and explained. This dual contribution – the model and the method – lays the foundation for a structured, traceable, and stakeholder-inclusive integration of trustworthiness including ethical concerns into AI design. The concept “trustworthiness including ethics” is used to reflect an integrated approach that encompasses both technical trustworthiness aspects (such as robustness and explainability) and ethical concerns (such as human agency, fairness, and privacy).

2.1 Trustworthiness including ethics values reference model

Trustworthiness and ethics are broad concepts, which meaning varies among stakeholders due to different perspectives and priorities within the industrial context. The definition of a reference model is required to standardise a common understanding and the information gathering among the stakeholders. This section presents the trustworthiness including ethics values reference model, defined for studying the trustworthiness and ethical requirements of AI solutions at different points in the lifecycle and by different stakeholders: product owners, AI developers, AI evaluators and end-users. Although multiple sources of literature were examined, the principal sources used to define this model are: Ethically Aligned Design (EAD) [6] and Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) [7]. From this analysis, a set of nine values, each one split into sub-values, are identified (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Trustworthiness including ethics reference model: values and sub-values.

2.2 Trustworthiness including ethics values implementation method

This section presents the trustworthiness including ethics values implementation method. It is composed by two phases (see Fig. 2): Phase 1. Trustworthiness including ethics by design and Phase 2. Ethics and legal impact assessment.

Fig. 2. Trustworthiness and ethics values implementation method: phases and stages

This implementation method is operationalised through the Value Sensitive Design (VSD) approach, which supports the early integration of values into the AI system design. Considering the values presented in section 2.1, two value domains are distinguished:

- **Technical values**, which are internal to the system and relate to its functionality and performance. These include robustness, explainability, traceability, and safety. During Phase 1 these values are first assessed by means of AI algorithm-level toolchains (e.g., robustness testing, confidence calibration). Then, they are embedded into the AI system and assessed again at system level.
- **Ethical values**, which are outward-facing and pertain to the system's interaction with users and its impact on society. These include human agency, fairness, privacy, and prevention of misuse. These are addressed through design decisions and governance features such as oversight interfaces, auditability, and fallback mechanisms, and are later examined during Phase 2.

One of the main benefits of this dual approach is to be able to look at AI-based solutions from two points of view, making it possible to collect different types of information, obtained by different means, from different stakeholders and throughout the AI lifecycle. Also, this implementation method does not only ensure compliance with current and evolving regulatory expectations, but also reinforces traceability between design intentions and deployment consequences, in line with the industry challenges for responsible AI development.

Phase 1. Trustworthiness including ethics by design.

In this phase, a requirements inventory is designed to help in the identification of the relevant values and sub-values for the AI-based solution. In this sense, every sub-value from the reference model is analysed. From this analysis, different requirements

associated to every sub-value are identified and added to the inventory. The goal is to use this inventory to support each stakeholder in the reflection about the relevance of the specific trustworthiness and ethical values and sub-values for the AI-based solution.

Phase 1 is split into four stages (see Fig 3). In Stage 1, during the requirements elicitation of the AI-based solution, the product owners go through the proposed requirements inventory, indicating for each requirement if it is relevant for their AI solution and establishing a priority. In stages 2 and 3, the aim is to gain insight on how trustworthiness and ethical requirements are covered during the design development of the AI solution, and finally during its evaluation. With this purpose, a checkpoint document is used to gather the information from AI developers (stage 2) and AI evaluators (stage 3). Finally, all this information is analysed and reviewed considering all the perspectives, providing a global trustworthiness and ethical assessment of the AI-based solution from a system perspective. The aim of this phase is to provide traceability among relevance and priority, mitigating trustworthiness, ethical and legal risks across AI life cycle early from the design phase.

Fig. 3. Stages under phase 1 “Trustworthiness including ethics by design”.

Phase 2. Ethics and legal impact assessment.

The second phase of the implementation method addresses the verification of ethical and legal risks associated with the AI system, complementing the values captured during design. While Phase 1 embedded values within the system architecture, Phase 2 evaluates their real-world implications, focusing on system accountability, legal exposure, and societal alignment. This phase adopts a formal methodology based on the AI Impact Assessment framework described in ISO/IEC 42005 [ISO/IEC 42005: AI System Impact Assessment, International Organization for Standardization, 2024], adapted for research contexts. It is structured around a detailed questionnaire covering technical, legal, social, and ethical dimensions of impact. The methodology also incorporates regulatory references, including the GDPR, AI Act, and related cybersecurity legislation, synthesised into a Legal Impact Summary Chart.

3 Results

The presented reference model and its implementation method have been applied in an industrial context involving collaborative robotics (cobots). This context consists in a human-shared workshop, where robotic manipulators pick components from containers and place them on an assembly table for human operators, who then assemble the parts and return them for transport by a mobile robot to the warehouse. The primary goal is

to enhance the reliability and efficiency of robotic support using AI functionalities, contributing to improved safety through human detection and tracking, as well as anomaly detection (unsafe situations, safety gestures). Also, it facilitates smoother human-robot coordination during tasks such as part handovers, ultimately boosting overall operational efficiency.

3.1 Implementation and results in the cobots industrial context

This section provides a summary of the results obtained so far, showing the relationship with the research questions (RQ) identified in the introduction. RQ1 and RQ2 are addressed by adopting the implementation method described in section 2.2. The implementation method allows these RQs to be answered in the affirmative, since two of its goals are precisely: Goal 1) Throughout the AI lifecycle, different stakeholders are consulted on the technical and ethical aspects that they consider to be a priority to focus on; Goal 2) Technical evaluations of AI-based solutions are conducted and the opinions of end-user representatives are gathered. This approach enables the collection of both qualitative and quantitative insights on the trustworthiness and ethics of the AI-based solution. Goal 1 is traced to RQ1 while goal 2 is traced to RQ2.

At the time of writing this paper, stages 1 and 2 have been fully implemented in the cobots industrial context, while stages 3 and 4 as well as Phase 2 are ongoing work. RQ4 and RQ5 cannot yet be answered based on the current results of the study. The rest of this section explains insights obtained as a result of Stages 1 and 2, which can be traced to RQ3.

Table 1. Number of requirements considered for each trustworthiness and ethics value.

Value	Total	Requirements prioritised by product owner (Stage 1)	Requirements prioritised by AI developer (Stage 2)
Accountability	6	5	0
Awareness of misuse	1	0	0
Competence	3	1	0
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness	6	1	0
Human autonomy	7	5	3
Privacy and data governance	7	6	2
Societal and environmental wellbeing	3	1	0
Technical robustness and safety	12	10	2
Transparency	7	7	4
Total	52	36	11

Table 1 shows the number of requirements considered during Stages 1 & 2. From the total of 52 requirements of the “Trustworthiness and ethics values reference model”, during Stage 1, 36 requirements (69,23%) are considered by product owners as key requirements for the AI-based solution to be developed. During Stage 2, AI developers have considered 11 requirements for being addressed during the implementation

activities. Analysing data in Table 1, it can be appreciated that trustworthiness and ethics requirements are mainly concentrated into 4 values: *human autonomy, privacy and data governance, technical robustness and safety* and *transparency*. It is worth noting that these values are the ones with the highest percentage of requirements identified in the reference model, showing their importance in terms of accomplishment for the AI-based solutions. Both, product owners and AI developers have focused their main interest in those values. This first finding provides an insight into RQ3 “Are the different stakeholders prioritising the same trustworthiness and ethics requirements?”.

Also, Fig. 4 shows how related values are considered by product owner and AI developer. It can be appreciated that there is a value considered of high importance for product owners (Accountability, which includes auditability) but not prioritized by AI developers. However, AI developers have prioritized the Transparency value, which includes traceability and explainability. A relationship between Accountability and Transparency value is identified since auditing an AI system (part of Accountability) will need first to define mechanisms for traceability and explainability (part of Transparency). One conclusion that can be drawn is that, although a priori it seems that product owners and AI developers are focusing on different values, the values of accountability and transparency are closely related. This second finding also provides an insight into RQ3 “Are the different stakeholders prioritising the same trustworthiness and ethics requirements?”.

Fig. 4. Prioritised requirements by product owners and AI developers.

4 Conclusion, limitations and future work

Currently the main limitation is related to the unavailability of definitive results for the ongoing activities (as explained in section 3.1), and therefore to not yet having a definitive assessment for all the method phases and stages. The future work is to have these results available and to analyse how RQ4 and RQ5 can be answered. The preliminary findings in the work suggest that AI trustworthiness including ethics is a broad concept that must be analysed taking into consideration the different stakeholder

perspectives and priorities together with industrial context. The proposed reference model and implementation method bridge this gap, transforming abstract ethical concerns into actionable and traceable requirements that are progressively addressed across the AI lifecycle. Therefore, the approach presented in this paper provides one integrated end-to-end process addressing trustworthiness and ethical alignment across the AI lifecycle and engaging all relevant stakeholders. Preliminary results demonstrate that achieving trustworthy AI, including its ethical and societal dimensions, requires not only sound technical design and evaluation, but also the structured integration of values and stakeholder priorities, as shown in the implementation and assessment of the collaborative robotics use case. The approach presented in this paper provides a traceable chain from early design values to final AI product accountability, standardising both technical and legal perspectives under this framework.

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